

COMPOSITION AND FINALITY OF THE MIXED FLOCKS IN SEABIRDS AT ILHA COMPRIDA ISLAND, (SÃO PAULO, BRAZIL).

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Introduction.

Shorebirds are a diverse group of mostly small, long-legged, gregarious birds that live along shorelines and inland waterways worldwide. They fly swiftly in large flocks migrating long distances between their seasonal ranges. The visual impression one gets is of speed and numbers, as entire flocks of tens of thousands of shorebirds are able to elude the fastest of winged predators (1). Shorebirds typically have long, slender legs and bills, relatively long, pointed wings, short tails, and a streamlined body. These features reflect a lifestyle of wading in water, marshes, or mudflats. Shorebirds primarily probe for burrowing invertebrates for food. They also make long-distance migrations between summer breeding and winter foraging areas which requires great strength and endurance. Most shorebirds are commonly found in tidal environments where they spend roughly half of their lives feeding. The rest is spent in flight, on migration, or living in wet meadows or upland grassy fields (2). In Ilha Comprida, 18 species of shorebirds occur regularly. Most occur during the nonbreeding season. Except for a few species, shorebirds are grouped into two large families: the Charadriidae (plover family), Scolopacidae (sandpiper family) and coastalbird in Laridae (Gulls and terns). The two groups can generally be distinguished from each other by their feeding habits. Plovers with their large eyes feed by sight, using a run-peck-run strategy. Sandpipers have small eyes but specialized bills that they use as probes, employing the "sewing machine" method of continuous searching. Shorebird diets are quite varied and change with the seasons and the habitat. In this work we provide the record of composition and finality of the mixed flocks in shorebirds and coastalbird on Ilha Comprida Island, (São Paulo, Brazil).

Methods.

Ilha Comprida was formed by the accumulation of sandy sediments and is a prominent landscape at the southern coast of São Paulo State (lat 47° 50' W 24° 52' S). Bird censuses were carried out from 4 June 1999 to 6 May 2002, along all the stretch of 70 km of beach from the locality of Boqueirão Sul and northward to Icapara Channel. Coastal birds and shorebirds were counted on the northward journey from a vehicle moving at about 40Km/h along the lower beach. Such methodology was proposed by Bibby (3) for sandy beaches. The censuses were done in the morning periods from about 08:00 to 11:30 h, during ebb tides, when weather and traffic conditions were good. Weekly Sampling added up a total of 140 samples. Each census had minimum duration of 2:30 hours of observation and maximum of 4:00 hours. Binoculars (7X50 and 20X60) were used for observations.

Results and Discussion.

The results indicate a total of 188 flocks were observed, 120 belonging to marine ecosystems and the remaining 68 belonging to the estuarine environmental. The highest average species numbers were 4 and 6,7 respectively from estuarine environmental and sandy beaches. Of the flocks from sandy beaches, 76% were feeding and 24% were resting. Of the water shelf flocks, 72% were seen feeding while all the flocks from estuarine environmental were 76% resting (Table 1). Most shorebirds occur in mixed flocks at Ilha Comprida beach during migration, which peaks in early-to-mid October and November when they arrive in very large numbers of mixed flocks. Many return in the fall on their southbound migration as well. Spotted sandpipers (*Actitis macularia*), semipalmated plovers (*Charadrius semipalmatus*) were registered in mangrove environmental. Greater yellowlegs (*Tringa melanoleuca*), lesser yellowlegs (*Tringa flavipes*), solitary sandpiper (*Tringa solitaria*), sanderlings (*Calidris alba*) and *Calidris fuscicollis* have been found foraging in sandy beach in the mesotidal zone. Only one species have been found nesting in the dune, this species was collared plover (*Charadrius collaris*). The frequency of the species record in the sandy beach, mangrove and coastal water in mixed flocks is represented in table 2. During resting, the coastal birds locally occur, in bigger numbers all around the shore of South of the Ilha Comprida island. Their presence of the mixed flocks were most readily observed at Boqueirão Sul, where the most species ever recorded. About 4000 individual can be seen on an average summer day in Boqueirão sul, including

thousands of gulls (*Larus dominicanus*), terns (*Sterna eurygnatha*, *S. maxima*, *S. hirundo*, *S. hirundinacea*) and cormoron (*Phalacrocorax brasiliensis*). Among the predominant species *Sterna eurygnatha* and *Sterna maxima* had larger registrations in the months of were most common in summer, forming, a lot of times heterospecific decrees flocks along the beach. *Sterna eurygnatha* was nearly always constant in practically every studied month, even so with exception at of November and December of 2001 in which its abundance declined that was accessory. In relation to relative abundance, in the year of 1999 it was dominant and abundant in almost every studied month, exception for January that was not very abundant. In the year 2000 there was the same tendency, however the month that they were not very abundant was the trend was similar except for lower abundance in December. In 2001 the species was rare in January and December and not very abundant in February and March, being dominant and abundant in the other studied months.

One of the most notable and beautiful characteristics of shorebirds is a particular behavioral adaptation - scattered feeders lift off and swiftly consolidate into a graceful flock at the approach of a predator. Each individual's chance of avoiding being eaten is then increased. Some shorebird species are generally solitary, but most will readily join a flock in response to a disturbance (4). Mixed-species flocks are common. Mixed flocks also make bird watching more fun for the beginner, who can use contrasts of size, color, or behavior to spot different species. These nomads travel in search of mudflats, or unvegetated shallows, where they can find aquatic invertebrates to satisfy their specialized diets. Whenever such accommodations are not present along their usual migration routes, like during floods, shorebirds must alter their flight patterns to find them. In other words, their fueling stops depend entirely on habitat conditions (5). The flocks size of shorebirds were influenced by location, activity (roosting, foraging), date, and environmental variables such as tide, cloud cover, temperature, and wind (6). The presence or absence of a predator also affects the size of shorebirds flocks (7) and coastal bird flocks. Our findings indicate that flock sizes of certain species are influenced by abundance and, by inference, seasonality and availability of habitat. Flying swiftly in mixed flocks, they look over all wetlands for suitable feeding and resting sites. Shallows six inches deep might bring down avocets that swing their upturned bills like scythes to stir up tiny minnows and aquatic invertebrates. Water fourinches deep might attract greater yellowlegs, while their close kin, lesser yellowlegs, are foraging in water two inches shallower. They might be accompanied by several species of "peeps"-sparrow-sized shorebirds that are tricky to tell apart -that probe the shoreline mud for food. Individual species in the mixed flocks still congregate in groups, it's likely the different species stay close to one another for mutual protection from predators such as hawks and falcons.

Conclusion.

The flocks size of shorebirds and seabird were influenced by location, activity (roosting, foraging), date, and environmental variables such as tide, cloud cover, temperature, and wind. The presence or absence of a predator, tourist and vehicles also affects the size of shorebirds flocks and coastal bird flocks. Our findings indicate that flock sizes of certain species are influenced by abundance and, by inference, seasonality and availability of habitat. Shorebirds and other migratory species which depend on swampy areas as stopovers are being forced to move to other regions, due to the fast environmental changes occurring in the landscape (8). In Ilha Comprida this process has started in the middle of the 80's, through fast urbanization. Flat and extensive areas adequate to real estate speculation, covered by the sandbanks, were firstly neglected by the persons eager to be closer to the beach due to the dunes invasion. In this district the anthropic action has been changed the island environment, mainly due to the real estate speculation associated to tourism and leisure. This situation can bring problems to the migratory birds, which uses the island as an important stopover in its migratory route.

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Table1- Behaviour and total number of the mixed flocks record in Ilha Comprida beach in different environmental: Sandy beach (SB), mangroves (MG), Costal water (CW), number of the specie (NS), individual number (IN).

Environmental	Total	NS	IN	Resting	Foraging
SB	143	18	6000	34 (24%)	108 (76%)
MG	46	8	30	11 (24%)	35 (76%)
CW	14	8	2000	4 (28%)	10 (72%)
Total	188	34	8300	95 (50%)	93 (49%)

Table 2 - Frequency (in %) of the species record in the sandy beach and coastal water in mixed flocks.

Species	Sandy beach	Estuarine environmental	Coastal water
<i>Actitis macularia</i>	6,0	94	0,0
<i>Arenaria interpres</i>	100	0,0	0,0
<i>Calidris alba</i>	100	0,0	0,0
<i>Calidris canutus</i>	100	0,0	0,0
<i>Calidris fuscicollis</i>	96	4,0	0,0
<i>Charadrius semipalmatus</i>	80	20	0,0
<i>Charadrius collaris</i>	90	10	0,0
<i>Fregata magnificens</i>	0,0	20	80
<i>Larus dominicanus</i>	50	20	30
<i>Numenius phaeopus</i>	90	10	0,0
<i>Phalacrocorax brasilianus</i>	10	80	10
<i>Pluvialis dominica</i>	100	0,0	0,0
<i>Pluvialis squatarola</i>	100	0,0	0,0
<i>Sterna eurygnatha</i>	60	20	20
<i>Sterna máxima</i>	70	10	10
<i>Sterna hirundinacea</i>	65	20	15
<i>Sterna hirundo</i>	70	0,0	30
<i>Sula leucogaster</i>	0,0	20	80
<i>Tringa flavipes</i>	100	0,0	0,0
<i>Tringa melanoleuca</i>	100	0,0	0,0
<i>Tringa solitária</i>	10	90	0,0
<i>Vanellus chilensis</i>	100	0,0	0,0